

Another wanderer from the Paleocene-
Eocene Thermal Maximum?
A new species of the North American snake genus
Cheilophis Gilmore, 1938 from the early Eocene of France

Georgios L. GEORGALIS & Bastien MENNECART

SNAKES FROM THE CENOZOIC OF EUROPE

– TOWARDS A MACROEVOLUTIONARY AND PALAEOBIOGEOGRAPHIC SYNTHESIS

Edited by Georgios L. GEORGALIS, Hussam ZAHER & Michel LAURIN

DIRECTEURS DE LA PUBLICATION / PUBLICATION DIRECTORS :
Gilles Bloch, Président du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle
Étienne Ghys, Secrétaire perpétuel de l'Académie des sciences

RÉDACTEURS EN CHEF / EDITORS-IN-CHIEF: **Michel Laurin*** (CNRS), Philippe Taquet (Académie des sciences)

ASSISTANTE DE RÉDACTION / ASSISTANT EDITOR: Adenise Lopes (Académie des sciences; cr-palevol@academie-sciences.fr)

MISE EN PAGE / PAGE LAYOUT: Audrina Neveu (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle; audrina.neveu@mnhn.fr); Pénélope Laurin

RÉVISIONS LINGUISTIQUES DES TEXTES ANGLAIS / ENGLISH LANGUAGE REVISIONS: Kevin Padian (University of California at Berkeley)

RÉDACTEURS ASSOCIÉS / ASSOCIATE EDITORS (*, *took charge of the editorial process of the article/a pris en charge le suivi éditorial de l'article*):

Micropaléontologie/*Micropalaeontology*

Lorenzo Consorti (Institute of Marine Sciences, Italian National Research Council, Trieste)

Paléobotanique/*Palaeobotany*

Cyrille Prestianni (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels)

Anaïs Boura (Sorbonne Université, Paris)

Métazoaires/*Metazoa*

Annalisa Ferretti (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, Modena)

Paléoichthyologie/*Palaeoichthyology*

Philippe Janvier (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Académie des sciences, Paris)

Amniotes du Mésozoïque/*Mesozoic amniotes*

Hans-Dieter Sues (Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington)

Tortues/*Turtles*

Walter Joyce (Universität Freiburg, Switzerland)

Lépidosauromorphes/*Lepidosauromorphs*

Hussam Zaher* (Universidade de São Paulo)

Oiseaux/*Birds*

Jingmai O'Connor (Field Museum, Chicago)

Paléomammalogie (mammifères de moyenne et grande taille)/*Palaeomammalogy (large and mid-sized mammals)*

Grégoire Métais (CNRS, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Sorbonne Université, Paris)

Paléomammalogie (petits mammifères sauf Euarchontoglires)/*Palaeomammalogy (small mammals except for Euarchontoglires)*

Robert Asher (Cambridge University, Cambridge)

Paléomammalogie (Euarchontoglires)/*Palaeomammalogy (Euarchontoglires)*

K. Christopher Beard (University of Kansas, Lawrence)

Paléoanthropologie/*Palaeoanthropology*

Aurélien Mounier (CNRS/Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris)

Archéologie préhistorique (Paléolithique et Mésolithique)/*Prehistoric archaeology (Palaeolithic and Mesolithic)*

Nicolas Teyssandier (CNRS/Université de Toulouse, Toulouse)

Archéologie préhistorique (Néolithique et âge du bronze)/*Prehistoric archaeology (Neolithic and Bronze Age)*

Marc Vander Linden (Bournemouth University, Bournemouth)

RÉFÉRÉS / REVIEWERS: <https://sciencepress.mnhn.fr/periodiques/comptes-rendus-palevol/referes-du-journal>

COUVERTURE / COVER:

Life reconstruction of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. Credits: Artwork by Jaime Chirinos.

Comptes Rendus Palevol est indexé dans / *Comptes Rendus Palevol is indexed by:*

- Cambridge Scientific Abstracts
- Current Contents® Physical
- Chemical, and Earth Sciences®
- ISI Alerting Services®
- Geoabstracts, Geobase, Georef, Inspec, Pascal
- Science Citation Index®, Science Citation Index Expanded®
- Scopus®.

Les articles ainsi que les nouveautés nomenclaturales publiés dans *Comptes Rendus Palevol* sont référencés par / *Articles and nomenclatural novelties published in Comptes Rendus Palevol are registered on:*

- ZooBank® (<http://zoobank.org>)

Comptes Rendus Palevol est une revue en flux continu publiée par les Publications scientifiques du Muséum, Paris et l'Académie des sciences, Paris
Comptes Rendus Palevol is a fast track journal published by the Museum Science Press, Paris and the Académie des sciences, Paris

Les Publications scientifiques du Muséum publient aussi / *The Museum Science Press also publish:*

Adansonia, Geodiversitas, Zoosystema, Anthropolozologica, European Journal of Taxonomy, Naturae, Cryptogamie sous-sections *Algologie, Bryologie, Mycologie*.

L'Académie des sciences publie aussi / *The Académie des sciences also publishes:*

Comptes Rendus Mathématique, Comptes Rendus Physique, Comptes Rendus Mécanique, Comptes Rendus Chimie, Comptes Rendus Géoscience, Comptes Rendus Biologies.

Diffusion – Publications scientifiques Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle

CP 41 – 57 rue Cuvier F-75231 Paris cedex 05 (France)

Tél. : 33 (0)1 40 79 48 05 / Fax : 33 (0)1 40 79 38 40

diff.pub@mnhn.fr / <https://sciencepress.mnhn.fr>

Académie des sciences, Institut de France, 23 quai de Conti, 75006 Paris.

© This article is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)
ISSN (imprimé / *print*): 1631-0683/ ISSN (électronique / *electronic*): 1777-571X

Another wanderer from the Paleocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum? A new species of the North American snake genus *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938 from the early Eocene of France

Georgios L. GEORGALIS

Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences,
Sławkowska 17, 31-016 Kraków (Poland)
georgalis@isez.pan.krakow.pl (corresponding author)

Bastien MENNECART

Naturhistorisches Museum Basel, Augustinergasse 2, 4056 Basel (Switzerland)

Submitted on 6 August 2024 | Accepted on 4 March 2025 | Published on 25 June 2025

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:84D1BF6A-C21D-4997-A7C1-79F1A6173E53](https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a16)

Georgalis G. L. & Mennecart B. 2025. — Another wanderer from the Paleocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum? A new species of the North American snake genus *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938 from the early Eocene of France, in Georgalis G. L., Zaher H. & Laurin M. (eds), Snakes from the Cenozoic of Europe – towards a macroevolutionary and palaeobiogeographic synthesis. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 24 (16): 317-331. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a16>

ABSTRACT

We here document new snake vertebral material from the early Eocene (MP 10) of Cuis, France, that we describe as a new species of *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938, a genus that was so far exclusively known from the Paleocene and Eocene of North America. The new taxon bears several anatomical features with the type, and so far, only known species of *Cheilophis* from North America. However, there are also important differences that allow us to recognize it as a new congeneric species. If our identification is correct, this first observed occurrence of *Cheilophis* from France adds another shared terrestrial vertebrate genus between Europe and North America, reinforcing biogeographic hypotheses about dispersals between the two landmasses around the Paleocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum (PETM).

RÉSUMÉ

Un autre vagabond du maximum thermique du Paléocène-Éocène? Une nouvelle espèce du genre de serpent nord-américain Cheilophis Gilmore, 1938 de l'Éocène précoce de France.

Nous documentons ici des vertèbres d'une nouvelle espèce de serpent provenant de l'Éocène inférieur (MP 10) de Cuis en France, que nous attribuons à *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938, un genre jusqu'à présent exclusivement connu durant l'Éocène de l'Amérique du Nord. Ce nouveau taxon présente plusieurs caractéristiques anatomiques en commun avec l'espèce type d'Amérique du Nord du genre *Cheilophis*, qui est jusqu'à présent la seule espèce connue. Mais nous observons également des différences importantes qui nous permettent de reconnaître les spécimens de Cuis comme appartenant à une nouvelle espèce congénérique. Si notre détermination est confirmée, cette première occurrence du genre *Cheilophis* observée en France ajoute un autre genre de vertébré terrestre partagé entre l'Europe et l'Amérique du Nord, renforçant les hypothèses biogéographiques concernant les dispersions entre les deux masses continentales à proximité du Maximum Thermique du Paléocène-Éocène (PETM).

KEY WORDS

Serpentes,
vertebral morphology,
dispersals,
Paléogène,
new species.

MOTS CLÉS

Serpentes,
morphologie des
vertèbres,
dispersions,
Paléogène,
espèce nouvelle.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of closely related, or even congeneric, terrestrial and fresh-water taxa in Europe and North America during the early and middle Eocene has been suggested to represent the product of dispersal(s) among the two landmasses during the Paleocene–Eocene Thermal Maximum (PETM) (e.g. McKenna 1975; Escarguel 1999; Smith & Smith 2010; Smith 2011; Rage 2013; Smith 2017; De Bast & Smith 2017; Georgalis & Joyce 2017; Hooker 2018; Smith & Georgalis 2022; Solé *et al.* 2022; Čerňanský *et al.* 2023, 2024; Mayr *et al.* 2024). This pattern has been repeatedly witnessed among numerous vertebrate groups, including amphibians, reptiles, flightless birds, and mammals (McKenna 1975; West & Dawson 1978; Estes & Hutchison 1980; Escarguel 1999; Smith *et al.* 2006; Smith & Smith 2010; Smith 2011; Rage 2013; Buffetaut & Angst 2014; Roček *et al.* 2014; Georgalis & Joyce 2017; Hooker 2018; Mourer-Chauviré & Bourdon 2020; Smith & Scanferla 2021; Smith & Georgalis 2022; Solé *et al.* 2022; Čerňanský *et al.* 2023, 2024; Conedera *et al.* 2024; Mayr *et al.* 2024). In particular, among reptiles, congeneric taxa in the Paleogene of both North America and Europe are documented for turtles (Georgalis & Joyce 2017; Pérez-García & Smith 2021), crocodylians (Brochu 2013), choristoderans (Sigogneau-Russell & Russell 1978; Erickson 1987), lizards (Sullivan 1979; Augé 2005, 2012; Smith 2009, 2011; Rage 2013; Smith *et al.* 2018; Augé *et al.* 2022; Čerňanský *et al.* 2023, 2024), and of course, snakes (Smith & Georgalis 2022).

Indeed, during the Eocene, Europe and North America hosted congeneric species of the snake genus *Dunnophis* Hecht *in* McGrew *et al.*, 1959 (see Rage 1973, 1974) and *Calamagras* Cope, 1873 (see Rage 1977). In addition, *Totlandophis* Holman & Harrison, 1998, was first recognized in the British late Eocene (Holman & Harrison 1998) but a congeneric species was subsequently established from the early Oligocene of Florida, United States (Holman & Harrison 2001). Although the congeneric affinities of some of these species have not been adequately tested (or these are even disputed, particularly the case of the European *Calamagras*; see Smith 2013; Smith & Georgalis 2022), these taxa have been used to suggest similar ophidian elements in the European and North American Eocene. In any case, it is currently accepted that certain, including non-congeneric but still closely related, snake taxa occurred in the Eocene of both Europe and North America (Smith & Scanferla 2021; Smith & Georgalis 2022). Besides, of course, there were also the aquatic snakes of the genus *Palaeophis* Owen, 1841, species of which were present in both the European and North American Eocene (see Smith & Georgalis 2022), but species of this genus are also known to inhabit the marine realm (Rage 1983; Georgalis *et al.* 2021a; Smith & Georgalis 2022), thus achieving a rather broad geographic distribution.

We here describe new vertebral material from the early Eocene (MP 10) of Cuis, East of Paris, France, which we refer to the North American genus *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938, previously known exclusively from the Paleocene and early Eocene of the United States. The new material from

France possesses several features in common with the type (and so far, only known) species of the genus, *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* Gilmore, 1938, but still enough differences that allow us to establish it as a new congeneric species. If our identification is correct, the new taxon from France adds a further genus of snakes shared in both the European and North American Eocene.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The fossil material described herein is permanently curated in the collections of the Natural History Museum of Basel (NMB). NMB collections are extensive for specimens from Cuis, including casts from the Lille Museum registered in 1940, and even older collections bought before. These old collections include mostly large mammals. Nevertheless, all fossil specimens of the new taxon described herein were found during more recent excavations, between 1976 and 1982. For comparative purposes, abundant material of extinct and extant snakes was studied at the collections of GMH, ISEZ, MGPT-MDHC, MNCN, MNHN, NHMUK, NHMW, PIMUZ, SMF-PH, and UM.

The X-ray microtomography of the holotype and paratype specimens of the new taxon was performed using a nanoCT[®] system nanotom[®] (phoenix X-ray, GE Sensing & Inspection Technologies GmbH, Wunstorf, Germany) hosted at the Biomaterials Science Center of the University of Basel (Switzerland), following these parameters: 1 440 equiangular radiographs were taken over 360° using an accelerating voltage of 170 kV and a beam current of 30 mA for a resolution of 10 µm. Specimen reconstruction has been made using Aviso Lite 9.0. 3D surface model reconstructions (.PLY files) of the holotype and paratype specimens of the new taxon are openly available in the online repository Morphosource (<https://www.morphosource.org/>). For details, see the section “Availability of materials and data” below.

Taxonomy follows Smith & Georgalis (2022). Anatomical terminology and measurements of snake vertebrae follow Georgalis *et al.* (2021b) and Szyndlar & Georgalis (2023).

ABBREVIATIONS

Institutional abbreviations

GMH	Geiseltalmuseum of Martin-Luther Universität Halle-Wittenberg, now referred to as the Geiseltalsammlung, housed as part of the Zentralmagazin Naturwissenschaftlicher Sammlungen, Halle;
ISEZ	Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków;
MGPT-MDHC	Massimo Delfino Herpetological Collection, Department of Earth Sciences, University of Torino;
MNCN	Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid;
MNHN	Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris;
NHMUK	Natural History Museum, London;
NHMW	Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna;
NMB	Naturhistorisches Museum Basel;
PIMUZ	Palaeontological Institute of the University of Zurich;

SMF-PH	Paleoherpetology collection, Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum, Frankfurt am Main;
UM	Institut des Sciences de l'Évolution, Université de Montpellier.

Other abbreviations

CL	centrum length;
EECO	Early Eocene Climatic Optimum;
NAW	neural arch width;
PETM	Paleocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum.

LOCALITY

Close to the town of Epernay, 140 km eastward from Paris (Marne, France), the Formation of Unios and Teredinids Sands, also known as “sables à unios et térédines” or “sables à térédines” in French, has yielded a very rich and diverse vertebrate fauna, notably in the localities of Grauves, Monthelon, Mancy, and Cuis (e.g. Stehlin 1909; Russell *et al.* 1982; Laurain *et al.* 1985; Duprat 1997). These sands have been deposited during a global retrograding deltaic context (Duprat 1997). The presence of both marine and freshwater fish, along with the wide variety of mammals (over 50 species have been recorded), confirm that these coarse sands belong to estuarine environments (Laurain *et al.* 1985; Duprat 1997). The faunal content indicates a local age of late Cuisian, which corresponds to late Ypresian, early Eocene (Jaeger 1971; Laurain *et al.* 1985; Duprat 1997). The Cuis fauna (Fig. 1), as well as the one from Monthelon and Mancy, has been attributed to the MP 10 reference level (Biochrom'97 1997; Escarguel *et al.* 1997). In Cuis, many mammals have been discovered, including several species of the rodent *Ailuravus* (Wood 1976), diverse carnivorous mammals (Mesonychidae: Solé *et al.* 2017; Hyaenodonta: Solé *et al.* 2021), perissodactyls (Vautrin *et al.* 2021; Bronnert & Métais 2023), and artiodactyls (Erfurt & Métais 2007; Boivin *et al.* 2018). The Cuis locality was first defined as a biochronological reference by Thaler (1966) (see also Jaeger 1971). However, the locality of Grauves was ultimately chosen as the reference locality for MP 10 (Godinot 1987; Biochrom'97 1997). The numerical age of the Cuis fauna is estimated to 49.86 ± 0.455 Ma (Escarguel *et al.* 1997), during the elevated temperatures of the Early Eocene Climatic Optimum.

SYSTEMATIC PALAEOONTOLOGY

SERPENTES Linnaeus, 1758
 ALETHINOPHIDIA Nopcsa, 1923
 CONSTRICTORES Oppel, 1811
 (*sensu* Georgalis & Smith, 2020)

Genus *Cheilophis* Gilmore, 1938

TYPE SPECIES. — *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* Gilmore, 1938.

EMENDED DIAGNOSIS. — *Cheilophis* can be differentiated from all other snakes by its unique combination of features: wide haemal keel (on the posterior mid- and posterior trunk vertebrae) that

FIG. 1. — Map of the Department of Marne, showing the position of the locality of Cuis; in the inset, map of France, showing the position of Cuis (square) and the city of Paris (circle).

bears a constriction at around its mid-length and becomes wider and blunt wedged-shaped at its posterior termination; distinct “notches” of the haemal keel in ventral view; ventral expansion of the haemal keel in lateral view; thick neural spine that is mostly confined at the posterior portion of the neural arch; relatively thin zygosphenes with a distinct median lamina (“lip”) and prominent lateral lobes; moderately vaulted neural arch; deep posterior median notch of the neural arch; deep interzygapophyseal constriction; almost circular cotyle and condyle; widely extended parapophyseal process of the paradiapophyses; almost horizontal to only slightly dorsally inclined prezygapophyses; and large prezygapophyseal and postzygapophyseal articular facets. In addition to these vertebral characters, Rage (1984b) also indicated the following cranial features as diagnostic for the genus: palatal process of the maxilla directed backwards; surangular lamina of the compound bone higher than the prearticular; coronoid present.

Cheilophis periplanetes n. sp.
 (Figs 2–7)

[urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:97488C93-5A21-4B5F-8DB2-52964DD335F5](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2120311/v1)

TYPE MATERIAL. — **Holotype.** France • 1 specimen (a trunk vertebra); Cuis; Formation of Unios and Teredinids Sands; 49.86 ± 0.455 Ma; MP 10, late Ypresian (early Eocene); NMB T.S.1100 (Figs 2; 3). **Paratype.** France • 1 specimen (a trunk vertebra); Cuis; Formation of Unios and Teredinids Sands; 49.86 ± 0.455 Ma; MP 10, late Ypresian (early Eocene); NMB T.S.1101 (Figs 4; 5).

REFERRED SPECIMENS. — Five trunk vertebrae (NMB T.S.1063, NMB T.S.1067, NMB T.S.1071, NMB T.S.1084, and NMB T.S.1092). Tentatively also, an anterior trunk vertebra (NMB T.S.1065) and two caudal vertebrae (NMB T.S.1048 and NMB T.S.1066).

TYPE LOCALITY AND AGE. — All specimens originate from the locality of Cuis; MP 10 (around 49.86 Ma \pm 0.455), early Eocene.

ETYMOLOGY. — The new species epithet is from the Greek word “periplanetes” (“περιπλανητής”), which means “wanderer”, reflecting the potential wandering that occurred during the dispersals among North America and Europe.

FIG. 2. — Holotype trunk vertebra (NMB T.S.1100) of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. in anterior (A), posterior (B), dorsal (C), ventral (D), right lateral (E), and left lateral (F) views. Scale bar: 1 mm.

FIG. 3. — 3D μ CT images of holotype trunk vertebra (NMB T.S.1100) of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. in anterior (A), left anterodorsolateral (B), left posterolateral (C), dorsal (D), posterior (E), ventral (F), left lateral (G), posterodorsal (H), and right anterolateral (I) views. Scale bar: 1 mm.

DIAGNOSIS. — *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. can be referred to the genus *Cheilophis* on the basis of the full list of diagnostic vertebral features of the genus (see above). *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. can be differentiated from the type and only other known species of *Cheilophis*, i.e., *Cheilophis huerfanoensis*, by its much smaller size (centrum length [CL] almost half in size), shorter centrum, the absence of prezygapophyseal and postzygapophyseal articular facets, the shorter neural spine, the rare presence of paracotylar foramina, and the more dorsally expanded lateral lobes of the zygosphenes.

DESCRIPTION

Holotype

The holotype vertebra (NMB T.S.1100) is incomplete, missing most of the left postzygapophysis and part of the right prezygapophysis, while the paradiapophyses are eroded (Figs 2; 3).

The vertebra has a centrum length (CL) of 3 mm and a neural arch width (NAW) of 3.2 mm. In anterior view (Figs 2A; 3A), the zygosphenes are moderately thin and bear a distinct median lamina, resembling a lip. There are two distinct lateral lobes on the zygosphenes that protrude much dorsally, like horns. The neural canal is semicircular (i.e., like an arch, rounded above and flat below). The prezygapophyses are almost horizontal, being only very slightly dorsally extended. The cotyle is large and almost circular. There are no paracotylar foramina. In posterior view (Figs 2B; 3E), the neural arch is moderately vaulted, with a vaulting ratio (sensu Georgalis *et al.* 2021b) equal to 0.47. The zygantral roof is relatively thick. The condyle is large and circular. In dorsal view (Figs 2C; 3D), the neural spine is very thick and is mostly confined to the posterior half of the neural arch. The zygosphenes are trilobed,

FIG. 4. — Paratype trunk vertebra (NMB T.S.1101) of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. in anterior (A), dorsal (B), left lateral (C), right lateral (D), ventral (E), and posterior (F) views. Scale bar: 1 mm.

with the two lateral lobes being more prominent than the central one. The prezygapophyses project anterolaterally. The prezygapophyseal articular facets are large and oval. The interzygapophyseal constriction is deep (unlike other Eocene European constrictors, such as *Eoconstrictor* Scanferla & Smith, 2020, and *Palaeopython* Rochebrune, 1880). The posterior median notch of the neural arch is deep. In ventral view (Figs 2D; 3I), the centrum is wider than long (ratio CL/NAW equal to 0.94). The haemal keel runs along most of the midline of the centrum; it commences anteriorly almost at the ventral level of the cotyle and terminates posteriorly at the level of the condyle. The width of the haemal keel is not consistent throughout its length; instead, there is a prominent constriction at the anterior half of the centrum and it becomes gradually wider and more prominent towards its posterior termination. Notably, there are distinct “notches” around its posterior portion. The subcentral grooves are deep. Subcentral foramina are present. The paradiapophyses are much eroded and their exact shape and size cannot be precisely deciphered, but it seems that they were not divided (or were only slightly divided) into distinct diapophyses and parapophyses. There are no prezygapophyseal accessory processes. The postzygapophyseal articular facets are massive and

broad. In lateral view (Figs 2E, F; 3G), the neural spine is very short; it commences far behind the level of the zygosphenes and gradually increases in height, being developed mostly at the posterior half of the neural arch. The zygosphenal facets are broad. The subcentral ridges are almost straight. The haemal keel protrudes ventrally at the level of the posterior half of the centrum, with its height gradually developed and culminating around its posteriormost edge. Judging from the width of the haemal keel, the vaulting of the neural arch, and the height of the neural spine, we assume that the vertebra originates somewhere from the mid- or posterior mid-trunk portion of the vertebral column.

Paratype

The paratype vertebra (NMB T.S.1101) is incomplete, missing both prezygapophyses and the right postzygapophysis (Figs 4; 5). The vertebra is small, with a centrum length (CL) equal to 2.8 mm and a neural arch width (NAW) equal to 3 mm. The paratype vertebra NMB T.S.1101 bears an overall resemblance to the holotype, exhibiting typical features of the species, such as the thin zygosphenes with the distinct “lip”, the prominent lateral lobes of the zygosphenes, the dorsoventrally short neural spine that is mostly confined to the

FIG. 5. — 3D μ CT images of paratype trunk vertebra (NMB T.S.1101) of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. in anterior (A), anterodorsal (B), left anterolateral (C), right anterolateral (D), dorsal (E), left lateral (F), ventral (G), ventrolateral (H), posteroventral (I), posterior (J), posterodorsal (K), and left posterolateral (L) views. Scale bar: 1 mm.

posterior portion of the neural arch, and the wide haemal keel with distinct “notches”. Nevertheless, there are some striking features observed in the paratype. Most prominently, the paratype vertebra exhibits the thickest neural spine known for the species (Figs 4B; 5E). Interestingly, the paratype vertebra NMB T.S.1101 demonstrates the widely extended parapophyseal process of the paradiapophyses (Fig. 5A, B), a feature that was highlighted as diagnostic for *Cheilophis* by Rage (1984a). This structure is otherwise not preserved in any other specimen of the new taxon (including the holotype [though a hint about such extended parapophyseal process might be observed on the right side of this specimen]) and thus, its observation in NMB T.S.1101 is of particular importance, as it further reinforces a referral of the new taxon from Cuis to the North American *Cheilophis*. The neural arch of NMB T.S.1101 is exceedingly depressed (Figs 4F; 5J), with a vaulting ratio (sensu Georgalis *et al.* 2021b) reaching only 0.16. The haemal keel is wide, and, similarly to the holotype, there

are distinct “notches” around its posterior portion (Figs 4E; 5G, H). What is further notable for NMB T.S.1101 is the presence of a small paracotylar foramen on the right of the cotyle (Figs 4A; 5A, B, D) – our observation of the μ CT files of this specimen confirms that this foramen goes relatively deeply into the vertebra. We attribute all these differences to intracolumnar variation. Judging from these features, we consider that the paratype vertebra NMB T.S.1101 originates from the posterior mid-trunk portion of the column (more posterior than the holotype).

Referred specimens – intracolumnar variation

All referred specimens are much incomplete but they nevertheless preserve certain anatomical structures that allow a taxonomic attribution to *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. Especially NMB T.S.1071, NMB T.S.1084, NMB NMB T.S.1092, and NMB T.S.1063 are all rather fragmentary and/or eroded. Most available trunk vertebrae share with the

FIG. 6. — Other referred vertebrae of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp.: A-F, anterior trunk vertebra NMB T.S.1065 in anterior (A), posterior (B), dorsal (C), ventral (D), left lateral (E), and right lateral (F) views; G-L, trunk (or cloacal) vertebra NMB T.S.1067 in anterior (G), posterior (H), dorsal (I), ventral (J), left lateral (K), and right lateral (L) views. Scale bars: 1 mm.

FIG. 7. — Caudal vertebrae tentatively referred to *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp.: **A-E**, anterior caudal vertebra NMB T.S.1048 in anterior (**A**), posterior (**B**), dorsal (**C**), ventral (**D**), and right lateral (**E**) views; **F-J**, posterior caudal vertebra NMB T.S.1066 in anterior (**F**), posterior (**G**), dorsal (**H**), ventral (**I**), and left lateral (**J**) views. Scale bars: 1 mm.

holotype an overall similar morphology, including a wider than long centrum, a thin zygosphenes with a median lamina (“lip”) and prominent lateral lobes that protrude dorsally, a relatively short neural spine that is mostly confined at the posterior portion of the neural arch, a moderately vaulted neural arch, absence of prezygapophyseal accessory processes, and large prezygapophyseal articular facets (Fig. 6). Nevertheless, some differences are apparent among the few available specimens, dealing with the shape and width of the haemal keel, the size of the prezygapophyseal and postzygapophyseal articular facets, and the height, anteroposterior length, and thickness of the neural spine. All these differences can most probably be attributed to intracolumnar variation (see e.g. Smith 2013; Szyndlar & Georgalis 2023) though some other kind of variation, such as ontogenetic (e.g. Georgalis & Scheyer 2019) cannot be excluded.

As is common in snakes, anterior trunk vertebrae are characterized by the presence of a hypapophysis instead of haemal keel, a more vaulted neural arch, and a higher and posteriorly inclined neural spine. The only anterior trunk vertebra from our sample is NMB T.S.1065 (Fig. 6A-F), though still a referral of this specimen to *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. should be considered as tentative. NMB T.S.1065 possesses hypapophysis (instead of haemal keel), which is short and posteroventrally directed, as well as a posteriorly inclined neural spine, which is considerably higher than in other vertebrae. Other differences include the narrower centrum and the (slightly) more vaulted neural arch. Nevertheless, other typical features of the new species are still present in the specimen NMB T.S.1065, such as the thin zygosphenes with a median lamina (“lip”) and two prominent lateral lobes, and the massive postzygapophyseal articular facets.

NMB T.S.1067 could be a posterior trunk vertebra (Fig. 6G-L), judging from the wide haemal keel, or even an anterior cloacal vertebra, judging from the high neural arch. However, features such as the not-so-short neural spine should make an exact intracolumnar assignment uncertain. Rage (1984b) had already highlighted that unlike most snakes, posterior trunk vertebrae of *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* did not possess short neural spines compared to preceding vertebrae, and therefore this observation may apply also to the new European species. Nevertheless, certain diagnostic features of the new species are apparent in this specimen, such as the zygosphenes with the “lip” and the distinct lateral lobes, as well as the massive prezygapophyseal and postzygapophyseal articular facets.

NMB T.S.1048 and NMB T.S.1066 are the only caudal vertebrae (Fig. 7) that are, at least tentatively, referred to *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. They are characterized by the presence of haemapophyses and pleurapophyses. These specimens too possess a thick neural spine that is confined to the posterior portion of the neural arch. Judging from the elongation of their centrum and the shape of the haemapophyses, NMB T.S.1048 originates from the anterior caudal region (Fig. 7A-E), while NMB T.S.1066 represents a posterior caudal vertebra (Fig. 7F-J). Interestingly, in the anterior caudal vertebra NMB T.S.1048, the haemapophyses are short and their base is situated onto a distinct keel in the centrum (Fig. 7A, B, D, E).

DISCUSSION

The genus *Cheilophis* was so far known exclusively by its type species, *Cheilophis huerfanoensis*, originally established by Gilmore (1938) based on abundant vertebrae and ribs,

presumably pertaining to a single individual, from the early Eocene (early Bridgerian) of the Gardner locality, Huerfano Formation, Colorado, United States. Gilmore (1938) figured only a single vertebra among this bulk of material, though he provided also some information on intracolumnar variation. Rage (1984b) further prepared the fossil skeleton described by Gilmore (1938), isolated several vertebrae that were embedded on matrix, highlighted errors in the original figuring of the vertebra provided by Gilmore (1938), designated and figured a lectotype, discussed intracolumnar variation, described and figured cranial elements (a maxilla, a dentary, and a compound bone) that were also embedded in the same matrix, and provided an emended diagnosis for the taxon. During the same year, in his monumental treatise on fossil snakes, the same author further figured an additional vertebra (a posterior trunk one) from the type locality (Rage 1984a). Some limited additional material has been subsequently referred to the same species from two other localities in the United States: a single, fragmentary, trunk vertebra from the early Eocene of the San Juan Basin, New Mexico (Sullivan & Lucas 1988), plus some limited vertebral material from the late Paleocene of New Jersey (Cook & Ramsdell 1991). Another vertebra, from the Oligocene of Nebraska, that was tentatively referred to *Cheilophis* by Gilmore (1938) was subsequently referred to another snake group later by Rage (1984b) and Holman (2000). *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* was further revised by Holman (2000), while Rage (2001) further highlighted diagnostic features of *Cheilophis* and comparisons with many other extinct and extant constrictors. The taxon was ultimately reviewed by Smith & Georgalis (2022), who continued to treat it as valid, though of still unclear relationships within Constrictores.

The new material from the early Eocene (MP 10) of Cuis bears several features that allow its referral to the North American genus, *Cheilophis*, including the so-called by Gilmore (1938: 80) “outstanding” “lip-like projection on the zygosphenes”, that inspired its very name (from the Greek word “χείλος” [“cheilos”], meaning “lip”). Several other shared features can be observed between the type species and *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. (see Diagnosis above). Notably, the new European taxon is considerably smaller than the American *Cheilophis huerfanoensis*, which achieved a CL of around 6 mm (vs around only 3 mm in *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp.).

The precise taxonomic affinities of *Cheilophis* are unresolved. Certain authors have suggested affinities of this genus with either colubriforms (Gilmore 1938), erycid booids (Erycinae of Hoffstetter 1955; Hoffstetter & Rage 1972), boids (Boinae of Holman 2000; Wallach *et al.* 2014), or generally with constrictors (Boinae of Rage 1984a, 1984b; Boidae of Underwood 1976; Smith & Georgalis 2022). The taxonomic allocation of multiple North American taxa to erycids has been subsequently criticized and/or rejected (Szyndlar & Rage 2003; Smith 2013; Smith & Georgalis 2022) and as a matter of fact, vertebrae of erycids can only be precisely identified only if they originate from the caudal portion of the column (Szyndlar & Georgalis 2023). Affinities of *Cheilophis* with boids could be indeed the case, but it should be noted that vertebrae of

many boids and pythonids share an overall similar vertebral morphology (see Szyndlar & Georgalis 2023) and both stem boids and stem pythonids have been identified in the European Eocene (Scanferla & Smith 2020; Zaher & Smith 2020; Georgalis *et al.* 2021b, 2025; Smith & Georgalis 2022; Smith & Scanferla 2022; Palci *et al.* 2024). The herein documented presence (even if rare, i.e., in only one specimen [the paratype NMB T.S.1101]) of paracotylar foramina in the new European taxon could possibly reject pythonoid affinities (as vertebrae of this group never possess paracotylar foramina) and support instead a possible inclusion within booids, vertebrae of which occasionally possess such foramina (see Szyndlar & Georgalis 2023). Nevertheless, although affinities with Booidea seem more likely, in the absence of more complete specimens, we still prefer to follow the opinion of Smith & Georgalis (2022) and keep *Cheilophis* as an *incertae sedis* within Constrictores.

It is now well known that several dispersals of terrestrial taxa occurred between North America and Europe, around the PETM, facilitated by global warming and the drastic palaeogeographic changes that occurred at this time period (McKenna 1975; Smith *et al.* 2006; Brikiatis 2014). Various dispersal routes have been proposed to explain this biogeographic pattern of shared vertebrate taxa among Eocene Europe and North America. Burbrink & Lawson (2007) attempted to analyze such dispersal routes among the two landmasses, mainly under the prism of snakes. According to these authors, potential pathways for these dispersal routes involved (Burbrink & Lawson 2007):

- the Thulean Bridge (i.e., Europe-British Islands-southern Greenland-Queen Elizabeth Islands), which consists of paratropical/polar broad-leafed forest, with a relatively warm climate, suitable for snakes and other reptiles;
- De Geer Bridge (i.e., Scandinavia-northern Greenland-Canadian Arctic Archipelago), which consists of para-tropical to temperate woodlands, with a cool climate, not very suitable for snakes and other reptiles;
- and Greenland-Faeroes Bridge (i.e., Greenland-Faeroes bridge [island chain connection]), which consists of paratropical/sub-tropical to temperate woodlands, with a relatively cool climate, not very suitable for snakes and other reptiles.

It is worth noting that particularly the De Geer and the Thulean routes have been proposed for the dispersals of other early Paleogene reptiles, such as crocodylians (e.g. Conedera *et al.* 2024) and lizards (Čerňanský *et al.* 2024). Furthermore, even if there was not some fully terrestrial corridor but only nearby landmasses, overwater dispersal has been well documented among snakes and has been variously used to explain molecular data (e.g. Kyriazi *et al.* 2013) and extralimital occurrences of the fossil record (e.g. Georgalis & Szyndlar 2022).

Whatever the exact dispersal route of these taxa may have been, what remains unambiguous is that multiple closely related taxa existed in both North America and Europe during the Eocene. The herein recognition of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. from the early Eocene (MP 10) of France further adds one more genus that had shared presence in both landmasses during the early Paleogene. The two type localities of the two species of *Cheilophis* appear to be more

FIG. 8. — Life reconstruction of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. Credits: Artwork by Jaime Chirinos.

or less of the same age: Cuis pertains to MP 10, i.e., bears an age of 49.86 ± 0.455 Ma (Escarguel *et al.* 1997), while the Gardner Locality is situated at the upper bed of the Huerfano Formation (Sullivan 1979), with an age of 50.3–49 Ma (Rasmussen *et al.* 2020). This almost contemporary age of both type localities affords no definite assumptions about the origin of *Cheilophis*, i.e., if the genus appeared earlier in North America and subsequently dispersed to Europe or vice versa. It should be noted though that the limited vertebral material from the late Paleocene of New Jersey that was referred to *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* by Cook & Ramsdell (1991) may hint towards an American ancestry, but of course, it still remains to be confirmed whether such taxonomic identification of the New Jersey referred material is indeed correct. Accordingly, we may tentatively assume that the ancestry of *Cheilophis* as well lies in North America.

The period (MP 10) that *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. has been found seems to correspond to a time interval of relative stability without major faunal events (Solé *et al.* 2019); this period is even considered as a period of endemism in Europe (Solé *et al.* 2022). Then, the dispersal of this species may have occurred earlier, probably during the Mammal Dispersal Event (MDE) at the PETM. The geographical origin of the Eocene vertebrate taxa has been strongly discussed over the past decades and Asia may represent a good candidate for several mammal groups (e.g. Godinot & Lapparent de Broin

2003; Smith *et al.* 2006; Smith & Smith 2010; Rose *et al.* 2014; De Bast & Smith 2017), while Europe and America may be for others (e.g. De Bast & Smith 2017; Boivin *et al.* 2018). Dispersals between Europe and Africa were also not uncommon during the early Eocene (e.g. Gheerbrant *et al.* 2006; Rage & Gheerbrant 2020; see discussion in Georgalis 2021). Nevertheless, Europe would have been a stepping stone most of the time to colonize North America around the PETM dispersal events (Smith *et al.* 2006; Rose *et al.* 2014; Solé *et al.* 2015). Moreover, Europe may be considered as the center of dispersion for the large flightless birds Gastornithidae (Buffetaut & Angst 2014; Mayr *et al.* 2024), while a diversity of insects may have originated from Greenland before dispersing into Northern America and Europe (Archibald & Makarkin 2006; Archibald *et al.* 2011). Regarding reptiles, many of the terrestrial / semiaquatic taxa that are shared among the European and North American Paleogene have usually their oldest occurrences (and suggested ancestry) in North America (e.g. the large trionychid *Axestemys* Hay, 1899; Vitek & Joyce 2015 vs Georgalis & Joyce 2017), but admittedly the coeval Asian and African fossil record is rather poor to afford further biogeographic implications.

The very small size (almost half centrum length, compared to the North American congeneric species) could potentially suggest different climatic and environmental adaptations between the European and North American species. In

any case, *Cheilophis*, being represented in Europe solely by the herein described material from Cuis, seems not to have survived for long in Europe. Indeed, its absence from all younger Eocene localities from Europe and elsewhere may indicate that the genus made it only for a brief period in Europe and eventually became extinct. As a matter of fact, Cuis coincides with the Early Eocene Climatic Optimum (EECO), which represents along with the PETM the highest temperatures for the last 65 Ma. Accordingly, this might explain why some “tropical” taxa and “newcomers” could not make it very long after that time in Europe.

The new material from Cuis further adds to the, so far limited, fossil record of snakes from the early Eocene of Europe. During this time interval, snake faunas in Europe are mainly represented by palaeophiids and to a lesser degree by constrictors, russellophiids, nigerophiids, archaeophiids, anomalophiids, scolecophidians, plus some alethinophidians of uncertain affinities (Smith & Georgalis 2022). As a matter of fact, early Eocene snake fossil remains from Europe have only been formally described from the Belgian localities of Dormaal, Quenast, Egem, Nederokkerzeel, and Woluwé Saint-Étienne in Van Pachtenbeke, the Danish locality of Isle of Fur, the French localities of Condé-en-Brie, La Borie, Grauves, Prémontéré, Cuise-la-Motte, and Cos, the German locality of Katharinenhof, the Italian locality of Monte Bolca, the Portuguese locality of Silveirinha, the English localities of Kingston, Isle of Sheppey, Bracklesham, and the Ukrainian locality of Sbornaya (for details and references see Smith & Georgalis 2022; see also Čerňanský *et al.* 2025). The majority of these localities yielded only palaeophiid remains, but a few continental localities (e.g. Dormaal, Condé-en-Brie, Grauves, Prémontéré, Cos, Silveirinha) yielded also some non-aquatic taxa. To these localities and taxa, we now add Cuis and the new constrictor *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. (Fig. 8), which provide interesting insights into the fascinating, but still obscure, biogeography and evolution of early Eocene snakes from Europe.

Acknowledgements

GLG acknowledges funding from the research project no. 2023/49/B/ST10/02631 financed by the National Science Center of Poland (Narodowe Centrum Nauki). GLG also acknowledges funding support from SYNTHESYS FR-TAF_Call4_035 (MNHN), for enabling him to travel and study the fossil snake collections at MNHN and further thanks the curator Nour-Eddine Jalil for his hospitality and support during that stay. We also thank Krister Smith (SMF-PH) for sharing photographs of the holotype and referred specimens of *Cheilophis huerfanoensis*. We would also like to thank Florian Dammeyer for his help with the NMB collections. Georg Shulz (Biomaterials Science Center, University of Basel) and Loïc Costeur (NMB) are much thanked for providing μ CT data. Kacper Węgrzyn (ISEZ) helped with 3D imaging. We finally thank Jaime Chirinos for the life reconstruction of the new species, presented in Figure 8. The quality of the manuscript was enhanced by the useful comments provided by two anonymous reviewers.

Availability of materials and data

All fossil specimens described herein are permanently curated at the collections of the Naturhistorisches Museum Basel, Switzerland. 3D surface model reconstructions (.PLY files) of the holotype and paratype specimens of *Cheilophis periplanetes* n. sp. are openly available in the online repository Morphosource (<https://www.morphosource.org/>): holotype trunk vertebra NMB T.S.1100 (Morphosource.org: Media 000741028 [ark:/87602/m4/741028]); paratype trunk vertebra NMB T.S.1101 (Morphosource.org: Media 000741048 [ark:/87602/m4/741048]).

REFERENCES

- ARCHIBALD S. B. & MAKARKIN V. N. 2006. — Tertiary giant lacewings (Neuroptera: Polystoechotidae): revision and description of new taxa from western north America and Denmark. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology* 4 (2): 119-155. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1477201906001817>
- ARCHIBALD S. B., JOHNSON K. R., MATHEWES R. W. & GREENWOOD D. R. 2011. — Intercontinental dispersal of giant thermophilic ants across the Arctic during early Eocene hyperthermals. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 278: 3679-3686. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2011.0729>
- AUGÉ M. 2005. — Évolution des lézards du Paléogène en Europe. Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (Mémoires du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle; 192), Paris, 369 p.
- AUGÉ M. 2012. — Amphisbaenians from the European Eocene: a biogeographical review. *Palaeobiodiversity and Palaeoenvironments* 92: 425-443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12549-012-0104-6>
- AUGÉ M. L., FOLIE A., SMITH R., PHÉLIZON A., GIGASE P. & SMITH T. 2022. — Revision of the oldest varanid, *Saniwa orsmaleensis* Dollo, 1923, from the earliest Eocene of northwest Europe. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 21 (25): 511-529. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2022v21a25>
- BIOCHROM'97 1997. — Synthèses et Tableaux de corrélations, in AGUILAR J.-P., LEGENDRE S. & MICHAUX J. (eds), *Actes du Congrès Biochrom'97, Montpellier, 14–17 avril : biochronologie mammalienne du cénozoïque en Europe et domaines reliés*. École pratique des hautes études, Institut de Montpellier (Mémoires et travaux de l'Institut de Montpellier; 21), Montpellier: 768-805.
- BOIVIN M., ORLIAC M. J., ANTUNES TELLES M., GODINOT M., LAURENT Y., MARANDAT B., VIDALENC D. & TABUCE R. 2018. — New material of *Diacodexis* (Mammalia, Artiodactyla) from the early Eocene of Southern Europe. *Geobios* 51 (4): 285-306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2018.06.003>
- BRIKIATIS L. 2014. — The De Geer, Thulean and Beringia routes: key concepts for understanding early Cenozoic biogeography. *Journal of Biogeography* 41 (6): 1036-1054. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12310>
- BROCHU C. A. 2013. — Phylogenetic relationship of Paleogene ziphodont eusuchian and the status of *Pristichampsus* Gervais, 1853. *Earth Environmental Sciences Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh* 103 (3-4): 521-550. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755691013000200>
- BRONNERT C. & MÉTAIS G. 2023. — Early Eocene hippomorph perissodactyls (Mammalia) from the Paris Basin. *Geodiversitas* 45 (9): 277-326. <https://doi.org/10.5252/geodiversitas2023v45a9>
- BUFFETAUT E. & ANGST D. 2014. — Stratigraphic distribution of large flightless birds in the Palaeogene of Europe and its palaeobiological and palaeogeographical implications. *Earth-Science Reviews* 138: 394-408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2014.07.001>

- BURBRINK F. T. & LAWSON R. 2007. — How and when did Old World ratsnakes disperse into the New World? *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 43 (1): 173-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2006.09.009>
- ČERNÁNSKÝ A., SMITH R., SMITH T. & FOLIE A. 2023. — Iguanian lizards (Acrodonta and Pleurodonta) from the earliest Eocene (MP 7) of Dormaal, Belgium: the first stages of these iconic reptiles in Europe. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 42 (4): e2184696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2023.2184696>
- ČERNÁNSKÝ A., SMITH R., SMITH T. & FOLIE A. 2024. — Timing of intercontinental faunal migrations: Anguimorph lizards from the earliest Eocene (MP 7) of Dormaal, Belgium. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 201: zlae082. <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlae082>
- ČERNÁNSKÝ A., GEORGALIS G. L., TABUCE R. & VIDALENC D. 2025. — The first snake from the lower Eocene (MP 10-11) of the Cos locality, Phosphorites du Quercy, France, in GEORGALIS G. L., ZAHER H. & LAURIN M. (eds), Snakes from the Cenozoic of Europe – towards a macroevolutionary and palaeobiogeographic synthesis. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 24 (5): 61-66. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a5>
- CONEDERA D., POCHAT-COTTILLOUX Y., RINDER N., ADRIEN J. & MARTIN J. 2024. — An anatomical reappraisal of the dwarf crocodylian *Arambourgia gaudryi* from the Eocene of Quercy (France) using CT data and its implications for the phylogeny and paleoecology of basally branching alligatoroids. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 43 (4): e2313612. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2024.2313612>
- COOK J. J. & RAMSDELL R. C. 1991. — Macrofossils from the Vincentown Formation (Paleocene) of New Jersey. *Bulletin of the New Jersey Academy of Sciences* 36 (1): 11-15.
- COPE E. D. 1873. — *Synopsis of new Vertebrata from the Tertiary of Colorado: obtained during the summer of 1873*. U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington D.C., 19 p. <https://doi.org/10.3133/70039707>
- DE BAST E. & SMITH T. 2017. — The oldest Cenozoic mammal fauna of Europe: implication of the Hainin reference fauna for mammalian evolution and dispersals during the Paleocene. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology* 15 (9): 741-785. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14772019.2016.1237582>
- DUPRAT M. 1997. — Les faciès à mammifères (MP6 à MP16) dans le Nord-Est du Bassin de Paris (France) : argumentation du modèle tectono-sédimentaire des dépôts paléogènes, in AGUILAR J.-P., LEGENDRE S. & MICHAUX J. (eds), *Actes du Congrès BiochroM'97, Montpellier, 14-17 avril : biochronologie mammalienne du cénozoïque en Europe et domaines reliés*. École pratique des hautes études, Institut de Montpellier (Mémoires et travaux de l'Institut de Montpellier; 21): 315-336.
- ERFURT J. & MÉTAIS G. 2007. — Endemic European Paleogene artiodactyls, in PROTHERO D. R. & FOSS S. E. (eds), *The evolution of artiodactyls*. The Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, MA: 59-84.
- ERICKSON B. R. 1987. — *Simoedosaurus dakotensis*, new species, a diapsid reptile (Archosauromorpha: Choristodera) from the Paleocene of North America. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 7 (3): 237-251. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.1987.10011658>
- ESCARGUEL G. 1999. — Les rongeurs de l'Eocene inferieur et moyen d'Europe Occidentale. Systematique, phylogenie, biochronologie et paleobiogeographie des niveaux-reperes MP 7 a MP 14. *Palaeovertebrata* 28 (2-4): 89-351.
- ESCARGUEL G., MARANDAT B. & LEGENDRE S. 1997. — Sur l'âge numérique des faunes de mammifères du Paléogène d'Europe Occidentale, en particulier celles de l'Éocène inférieur et moyen, in AGUILAR J.-P., LEGENDRE S. & MICHAUX J. (eds), *Actes du Congrès BiochroM'97, Montpellier, 14-17 avril : biochronologie mammalienne du cénozoïque en Europe et domaines reliés*. École pratique des hautes études, Institut de Montpellier (Mémoires et travaux de l'Institut de Montpellier; 21), Montpellier: 442-460.
- ESTES R. & HUTCHISON J. H. 1980. — Eocene lower vertebrates from Ellesmere Island, Canadian Arctic Archipelago. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 30: 325-347. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(80\)90064-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(80)90064-4)
- GEORGALIS G. L. 2021. — First pan-trionychid turtle (Testudines, Pan-Trionychidae) from the Palaeogene of Africa. *Papers in Palaeontology* 7 (4): 1919-1926. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spp2.1372>
- GEORGALIS G. L. & JOYCE W. G. 2017. — A review of the fossil record of Old World turtles of the clade *Pan-Trionychidae*. *Bulletin of the Peabody Museum of Natural History* 58 (1): 115-208. <https://doi.org/10.3374/014.058.0106>
- GEORGALIS G. L. & SCHEYER T. M. 2019. — A new species of *Palaeopython* (Serpentes) and other extinct squamates from the Eocene of Dielsdorf (Zurich, Switzerland). *Swiss Journal of Geosciences* 112: 383-417. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00015-019-00341-6>
- GEORGALIS G. L. & SMITH K. T. 2020. — Constrictores Oppel, 1811 – the available name for the taxonomic group uniting boas and pythons. *Vertebrate Zoology* 70 (3): 291-304. <https://doi.org/10.26049/VZ70-3-2020-03>
- GEORGALIS G. L. & SZYNDLAR Z. 2022. — First occurrence of *Psammophis* (Serpentes) from Europe witnesses another Messinian herpetofaunal dispersal from Africa – biogeographic implications and a discussion of the vertebral morphology of psammophiid snakes. *The Anatomical Record* 305 (11): 3263-3282. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.24892>
- GEORGALIS G. L., GUINOT G., KASSEGNE K. E., AMOUDJI Y. Z., JOHNSON A. K. C., CAPPETTA H. & HAUTIER L. 2021a. — An assemblage of giant aquatic snakes (Serpentes, Palaeophiidae) from the Eocene of Togo. *Swiss Journal of Palaeontology* 140 (20), 18 p. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13358-021-00236-w>
- GEORGALIS G. L., RABI M. & SMITH K. T. 2021b. — Taxonomic revision of the snakes of the genera *Palaeopython* and *Paleryx* (Serpentes, Constrictores) from the Paleogene of Europe. *Swiss Journal of Palaeontology* 140 (18), 140 p. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13358-021-00224-0>
- GEORGALIS G. L., ZAHER H. & LAURIN M. 2025. — Introduction to: Snakes from the Cenozoic of Europe – towards a macroevolutionary and palaeobiogeographic synthesis, in GEORGALIS G. L., ZAHER H. & LAURIN M. (eds), Snakes from the Cenozoic of Europe – towards a macroevolutionary and palaeobiogeographic synthesis. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 24 (3): 45-49. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a3>
- GHEERBRANT E., IAROCHENE M., AMAGHZAZ M. & BOUYA B. 2006. — Early African hyaenodontid mammals and their bearing on the origin of the Creodonta. *Geological Magazine* 143 (4): 475-489. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016756806002032>
- GILMORE C. W. 1938. — Fossil snakes of North America. *Geological Society of North America, Special Papers* 9: 1-96. <https://doi.org/10.1130/SPE9-p1>
- GODINOT M. 1987. — Mammalian reference levels MP1-10. *Münchner Geowissenschaftliche Abhandlungen A* 10: 21-23.
- GODINOT M. & LAPPARENT DE BROIN F. DE 2003. — Arguments for a mammalian and reptilian dispersal from Asia to Europe during the Paleocene-Eocene boundary interval. *Deinsea* 10: 255-275.
- HAY O. P. 1899. — Notes on the nomenclature of some North American fossil vertebrates. *Science* 10 (243): 253-254. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.10.243.253>
- HECHT M. K. 1959. — Amphibians and Reptiles, in MCGREW P. O., BERMAN J. E., HECHT M. K., HUMMEL J. M., SIMPSON G. G. & WOOD A. E. (eds), The geology and paleontology of the Elk Mountain and Tabernacle Butte area, Wyoming. *Bulletin of American Museum of Natural History* 117: 130-146. <http://hdl.handle.net/2246/1970>
- HOFFSTETTER R. 1955. — Sur les Boidés fossiles de la sous-famille des Érycinés. *Comptes rendus hebdomadaires des séances de l'Académie des Sciences de Paris* 240: 644-645.

- HOFFSTETTER R. & RAGE J.-C. 1972. — Les *Erycinae* fossiles de France (*Serpentes, Boidae*). Compréhension et histoire de la sous-famille. *Annales de Paléontologie* 58: 81-124.
- HOLMAN J. A. 2000. — *Fossil Snakes of North America: Origin, Evolution, Distribution, Paleoecology*. Indiana University Press, Bloomington and Indianapolis, 357 p.
- HOLMAN J. A. & HARRISON D. L. 1998. — A new genus of small boid snake from the upper Eocene of Hordle Cliff, Hampshire, England. *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 41: 29-33.
- HOLMAN J. A. & HARRISON D. L. 2001. — Early Oligocene (Whitheyen) snakes from Florida (USA): remaining boids, indeterminate colubroids, summary and discussion of the I-75 Local Fauna snakes. *Acta Zoologica Cracoviensia* 44: 25-36.
- HOOVER J. 2018. — Occlusal and morphogenetic field evolution in the dentition of European Nyctitheriidae (Euarctonta, Mammalia). *Historical Biology* 30 (1-2): 42-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2016.1276579>
- JAEGER J.-J. 1971. — La faune de Mammifères du Lutétien de Bouxwiller (Bas-Rhin) et sa contribution à l'élaboration de l'échelle des zones biochronologiques de l'Eocène européen. *Bulletin du Service de la carte géologique d'Alsace et de Lorraine* 24 (2-3): 93-105. <https://doi.org/10.3406/sgeol.1971.1386>
- KYRIAZI P., KORNILIOS P., NAGY Z. T., POULAKAKIS N., KUM-LUTAS Y., ILGAZ Ç., AVCI A., GÖÇMEN B. & LYMBERAKIS P. 2013. — Comparative phylogeography reveals distinct colonization patterns of Cretan snakes. *Journal of Biogeography* 40 (6): 1143-1155. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.12057>
- LAURAIN M., ALLOUC J., LEOURX J., LOUIS J., MONCIARDINI C. & MORFAUX P. 1985. — Notice explicative de la feuille Avize 1 / 50 000. *Carte géologique de la France* 158: 1-37.
- LINNAEUS C. 1758. — *Systema Naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis*. Laurentii Salvii, Stockholm, 824 p. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.542>
- MAYR G., MOURER-CHAUVIRÉ C., BOURDON E. & STACHE M. 2024. — Resurrecting the taxon *Diatryma*: a review of the giant flightless Eocene Gastornithiformes (Aves), with a report of the first skull of *Diatryma geiselsensis*. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 27 (3): a57. <https://doi.org/10.26879/1438>
- MCKENNA M. C. 1975. — Fossil mammals and early Eocene North Atlantic land continuity. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden* 62 (2): 335-353. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2395200>
- MOURER-CHAUVIRÉ C. & BOURDON E. 2020. — Description of a new species of *Gastornis* (Aves, Gastornithiformes) from the early Eocene of La Borie, southwestern France. *Geobios* 63: 39-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2020.10.002>
- NOPCSA F. 1923. — *Eidosaurus* und *Pachyophis*. Zwei neue Neocom-Reptilien. *Palaeontographica* 65: 99-154.
- OPPEL M. 1811. — Suite du 1er. memoire sur la classification des reptiles. Ord. II. Squammata mihi. Sect. II. Ophidii. Ord. III. Ophidii, Brongniart. *Annales du Muséum d'histoire Naturelle, Paris* 16: 376-393.
- OWEN R. 1841. — Description of some ophidiolites (*Palæophis tiliapicus*) from the London Clay of Sheppey, indicating an extinct species of serpent. *Transactions of the Geological Society Second Series* 6: 209-210. <https://doi.org/10.1144/transgslb.6.1.209>
- PALCI A., ONARY S., LEE M. S. Y., SMITH K. T., WINGS O., RABI M. & GEORGALIS G. L. 2024. — A new booid snake from the Eocene (Lutetian) Konservat-Lagerstätte of Geiseltal, Germany, and a new phylogenetic analysis of Booidea. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 202 (2): zlad179. <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlad179>
- PÉREZ-GARCÍA A. & SMITH T. 2021. — Systematics and diversity of the giant soft-shelled turtles (Cryptodira, Trionychidae) from the earliest Eocene of Belgium. *Geobios* 66-67: 15-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2020.07.006>
- RAGE J.-C. 1973. — Présence de *Dunnophis* (Reptilia, Serpentes) dans l'Eocène et l'Oligocène européens. *Compte rendu sommaire des séances de la Société Géologique de France* 1973 (3): 76-78.
- RAGE J.-C. 1974. — Les Serpents des Phosphorites du Quercy. *Palaeovertebrata* 6: 274-303.
- RAGE J.-C. 1977. — An erycine snake (Boidae) of the genus *Calamagras* from the French lower Eocene, with comments on the phylogeny of the Erycinae. *Herpetologica* 33 (4): 459-463. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3891716>
- RAGE J.-C. 1983. — Les serpents aquatiques de l'Éocène européen. Définition des espèces et aspects stratigraphiques. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Série 4, Section C, Sciences de la Terre, Paléontologie, Géologie, Minéralogie* 5: 213-241.
- RAGE J.-C. 1984a. — Serpentes, in WELLNHOFER P. (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Paleoherpétology*. Part 11. Gustav Fischer, Stuttgart, New York, 80 p.
- RAGE J.-C. 1984b. — The fossil snake *Cheilophis huerfanoensis* Gilmore, 1938, from Eocene of Colorado: redescription and reappraisal of relationships. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 3 (4): 219-222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.1984.10011977>
- RAGE J.-C. 2001. — Fossil snakes from the Paleocene of São José de Itaboraí, Brazil. Part II. Boidae. *Palaeovertebrata* 30: 111-150.
- RAGE J.-C. 2013. — Mesozoic and Cenozoic squamates of Europe. *Palaeobiodiversity and Palaeoenvironments* 93: 517-534. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12549-013-0124-x>
- RAGE J.-C. & GHEERBRANT E. 2020. — Island Africa and vertebrate evolution: a review of data and working hypotheses, in PRASAD G. V. R. & PATNAIK R. (eds), *Biological consequences of plate tectonics: New Perspectives on post-Gondwana break-up – A tribute to Ashok Sahni*. Springer, Cham: 251-264. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49753-8_10
- RASMUSSEN D. M., FOREMAN B. Z., FRICKE H. C., SNELL K., GIPSON L. & HOUSEN B. 2020. — The early Paleogene stratigraphic evolution of the Huerfano Basin, Colorado. *Rocky Mountain Geology* 55 (1): 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.24872/rmgjournal.55.1.1>
- ROČEK Z., WUTTKE M., GARDNER J. D. & BHULLAR B. A.-S. 2014. — The Euro-American genus *Eopelobates*, and a re-definition of the family Pelobatidae (Amphibia, Anura). *Palaeobiodiversity and Palaeoenvironments* 94: 529-567. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12549-014-0169-5>
- ROSE K., HOLBROOK L., RANA R., KUMAR K., JONES K. E., AHRENS H. E., MISSIAEN P., SAHNI A. & SMITH T. 2014. — Early Eocene fossils suggest that the mammalian order Perissodactyla originated in India. *Nature Communications* 5: 5570. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6570>
- ROCHEBRUNE A. T. DE 1880. — Revision des ophidiens fossiles du Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle. *Nouvelles Archives du Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, 2ème Série*, 3: 271-296.
- RUSSELL D. E., HARTENBERGER J.-L., POMEROL C., SEN S., SCHMIDT-KITTLER N. & VIANEY-LIAUD M. 1982. — Mammals and stratigraphy: the Paleogene of Europe. *Palaeovertebrata, Mémoire extraordinaire*: 1-77.
- SCANFERLA A. & SMITH K. T. 2020. — Exquisitely preserved fossil snakes of Messel: insight into the evolution, biogeography, habitat preferences and sensory ecology of early boas. *Diversity* 12: 100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d12030100>
- SIGOGNEAU-RUSSELL D. & RUSSELL D. E. 1978. — Étude ostéologique du reptile *Simoedosaurus* (Choristodera). *Annales de Paléontologie, Vertébrés* 64: 1-84.
- SMITH K. T. 2009. — Eocene lizards of the clade *Geiseltaliellus* from Messel and Geiseltal, Germany, and the early radiation of Iguanidae (Reptilia: Squamata). *Bulletin of the Peabody Museum of Natural History* 50 (2): 219-306. <https://doi.org/10.3374/014.050.0201>
- SMITH K. T. 2011. — The long-term history of dispersal among lizards in the early Eocene: new evidence from a microvertebrate assemblage in the Bighorn Basin of Wyoming, USA. *Palaeontology* 54 (6): 1243-1270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4983.2011.01107.x>

- SMITH K. T. 2013. — New constraints on the evolution of the snake clades Ungaliophiinae, Loxocemidae and Colubridae (Serpentes), with comments on the fossil history of erycine boids in North America. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 252 (2): 157-182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2012.05.006>
- SMITH K. T. 2017. — First crocodile-tailed lizard (Squamata: *Pan-Shinisaurus*) from the Paleogene of Europe. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 37 (3): e1313743. <https://doi.org/10.1080/102724634.2017.1313743>
- SMITH K. T. & GEORGALIS G. L. 2022. — The diversity and distribution of Palaeogene snakes - a review, with comments on vertebral sufficiency, in GOWER D. & ZAHER H. (eds), *The Origin and Early Evolution of Snakes*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge: 55-84. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108938891.006>
- SMITH K. T. & SCANFERLA A. 2021. — A nearly complete skeleton of the oldest definitive erycine boid (Messel, Germany). *Geodiversitas* 43 (1): 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.5252/geodiversitas2021v43a1>
- SMITH K. T. & SCANFERLA A. 2022. — More than one large constrictor lurked around paleolake Messel. *Palaeontographica, Abteilung A: Palaeozoology – Stratigraphy* 323 (1-3): 75-103. <https://doi.org/10.1127/pala/2021/0119>
- SMITH K. T., ČERNÁNSKÝ A., SCANFERLA A. & SCHAAL S. F. K. 2018. — Lizards and Snakes – Warmth-loving Sunbathers, in SMITH K. T., SCHAAL S. F. K. & HABERSETZER J. (eds), *Messel: An Ancient Greenhouse Ecosystem*. Schweizerbart, Stuttgart: 123-147.
- SMITH T. & SMITH R. 2010. — A new genus of “miacid” carnivoran from the earliest Eocene of Europe and North America. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 55 (4): 761-764. <https://doi.org/10.4202/app.2009.0125>
- SMITH T., ROSE K. D. & GINGERICH P. D. 2006. — Rapid Asia-Europe-North America geographic dispersal of earliest Eocene primate *Teilhardina* during the Paleocene-Eocene Thermal Maximum. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 103 (30): 11223-11227. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0511296103>
- SOLÉ F., SMITH T., TABUCE R. & MARANDAT B. 2015. — New dental elements of the oldest proviverrine mammal from the early Eocene of Southern France support possible African origin of the subfamily. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 60 (3): 527-538. <https://doi.org/10.4202/app.00146.2014>
- SOLÉ F., GODINOT M., LAURENT Y., GALOYER A. & SMITH T. 2017. — The European mesonychid mammals: phylogeny, ecology, biogeography, and biochronology. *Journal of Mammalian Evolution* 25: 339-379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10914-016-9371-8>
- SOLÉ F., PLATEAU O., LE VERGER K. & PHÉLIZON A. 2019. — New paroxyclaenid mammals from the early Eocene of the Paris Basin (France) shed light on the origin and evolution of these endemic European cimolestans. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology* 17 (20): 1711-1743. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14772019.2018.1551248>
- SOLÉ F., MORLO M., SCHAAL T. & LEHMANN T. 2021. — New hyaenodonts (Mammalia) from the late Ypresian locality of Prémontré (France) support a radiation of the hyaenodonts in Europe already at the end of the early Eocene. *Geobios* 66-67: 119-141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2021.02.004>
- SOLÉ F., FISCHER V., LE VERGER K., MENNECART B., SPEIJER R. P., PEIGNÉ S. & SMITH T. 2022. — Evolution of European carnivorous mammal assemblages through the Palaeogene. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 135 (4): 734-753. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blac002>
- STEHLIN H. G. 1909. — Remarques sur les faunules de Mammifères des couches éocènes et oligocènes du Bassin de Paris. *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France* 4: 488-520.
- SULLIVAN R. 1979. — Revision of the Paleogene genus *Glyptosaurus* (Reptilia, Anguillidae). *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 163: 1-72.
- SULLIVAN R. M. & LUCAS S. G. 1988. — Fossil Squamata from the San José Formation, early Eocene, San Juan Basin, New Mexico. *Journal of Paleontology* 62 (4): 631-639. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1305467>
- SZYNDLAR Z. & GEORGALIS G. L. 2023. — An illustrated atlas of the vertebral morphology of extant non-caenophidian snakes, with special emphasis on the cloacal and caudal portions of the column. *Vertebrate Zoology* 73: 717-886. <https://doi.org/10.3897/vz.73.e101372>
- SZYNDLAR Z. & RAGE J.-C. 2003. — *Non-erycine Booidea from the Oligocene and Miocene of Europe*. Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, 111 p.
- THALER L. 1966. — Les Rongeurs fossiles du Bas-Languedoc dans leurs rapports avec l'histoire des faunes et la stratigraphie du tertiaire d'Europe. *Mémoires du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Série C – Sciences de la Terre* 17: 1-295.
- UNDERWOOD G. 1976. — A systematic analysis of boid snakes, in BELLAIRS A. D'A. & COX C. B. (eds), *Morphology and Biology of Reptiles*. Linnean Society Symposium Series 3, Academic Press, London: 151-175.
- VAUTRIN Q., TABUCE R., LIHOREAU F., BRONNERT C., GHEERBRANT E., GODINOT M., METAIS G., YANS J., DUTOUR Y., VIALLE N., PHILIP J. & BILLET G. 2021. — New remains of *Lophiaspis maurettei* (Mammalia, Perissodactyla) from the Early Eocene of France and the implications for the origin of the Lophiodontidae. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 40 (6): e1878200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02724634.2020.1878200>
- VITEK N. S. & JOYCE W. G. 2015. — A review of the fossil record of New World turtles of the clade *Pan-Trionychidae*. *Bulletin of the Peabody Museum of Natural History* 56 (2): 185-244. <https://doi.org/10.3374/014.056.0204>
- WALLACH V., WILLIAMS K. L. & BOUNDY J. 2014. — *Snakes of the world: a catalogue of living and extinct species*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, London and New York, 1237 p.
- WEST R. M. & DAWSON M. R. 1978. — Vertebrate paleontology and the Cenozoic history of the North Atlantic region. *Polarforschung* 48: 103-119.
- WOOD A. E. 1976. — The paramyid rodent *Ailuravus* from the middle and late Eocene of Europe, and its relationships. *Palaeovertebrata* 7 (1-2): 117-149.
- ZAHER H. & SMITH K. T. 2020. — Pythons in the Eocene of Europe reveal a much older divergence of the group in sympatry with boas. *Biology Letters* 16 (12): 20200735. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2020.0735>

Submitted on 6 August 2024;
accepted on 4 March 2025;
published on 25 June 2025.